

Table 2. Results of artificially inoculating rices with GM. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Rice	Tillers (no./hill)	GM-affected tillers (no./hill)	Affected tillers (%)	Infestation score
ACM18 (IET7804)	15	0	0.0	0
IET9688	17	3	17.6	7
IET9690	12	2	16.7	7
IR20 (susceptible check)	14	6	42.9	7
Surekha (resistant check)	13	1	7.7	5

The same three rices were tested under artificial conditions. Five unemerged galls were introduced into each caged plant. After 25 d, percentage of affected tillers was 7.7 in resistant check Surekha, 42.9 in susceptible check IR20, and 0 in ACM18 (Table 2). □

Screening rice varieties with different growth durations for spider mite *Oligonychus oryzae* infestation

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Sixteen rice varieties with short, medium, and long growth durations were transplanted in 4- × 4-m plots in the field during 1986 wet season. An aqueous suspension of spider mite *O. oryzae* containing 100 adults/250 ml water was sprayed on rice foliage 10 d after transplanting.

Severe mite infestation 40 d after spraying caused yellowing. Mite populations (eggs, juveniles, and adults) were recorded from a 10 cm² leaf area on 10 hills/plot chosen at random.

No test variety was free from mite infestation (see table). The mite population was highest in long-duration

Spider mite populations in rice varieties of different growth durations. Cuttack, India, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Parents	Duration ^a (d)	Mites ^b (no./10 cm ²)
Subhadra	TNI/SR26-13	90 S	18.9 a
Bala	N22/TN1	105 S	20.4 a
Kalinga-II	AC540/Ratna	80 S	28.2 b
Vani	IR8/CR1014	125 M	28.9 b
Parijat	TKM6/TN1	115 M	30.0 b
Kesari	Kumar/Jagannath	95 S	30.6 b
Sattari	Mut-Sel (NSJ200/Padma)	70 S	32.6 b
Pankaj	Peta/Tonkai Rotan	145 L	34.0 b
Savitri	Pankaj/Jagannath	155 L	39.6 c
Utkal Prabha	Waikoku/CR1014	155 L	40.5 c
Karuna	IR8/Adt 27	125 M	47.8 d
Jaya	T141/TN1	130 M	50.8 d
Jagannath	T141 mutant	150 L	53.4 d
Ratna	TKM6/IR8	125 M	60.2 e
Vijaya	T90/IR8	140 L	62.8 e
CR1018	Culture	155 L	70.5 f

^aS = short duration, M = medium duration, L = long duration. ^bMean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

CR1018 and lowest in short-duration Subhadra. Within the same duration group, some varieties showed significantly different populations.

Population differences were not significant between all varieties of one duration and all varieties of another duration. □

Leafhopper (LF) epidemic in Haryana

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Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* historically has occurred only as a sporadic and minor rice pest. But during the 1987 wet season (kharif), it struck in an epidemic intensity. Karnal, Kurukshetra, Ambala, and Sirsa districts were badly damaged.

Infestation started the first week of Aug and lasted to the first week of Oct. Peak infestation was during the second week

LF damage on rice in Haryana, India, 1987.

Variety	Tillers/hill ^a			Leaves/hill ^b			Length/leaf			Larvae (no./10 leaves)
	No.	Affected	%	No.	Folded	%	Length (cm)	Length affected (cm)	%	
Jaya	8.3	5.8	70	44.2 (6.72)	30.5 (5.31)	47	46.4	9.4	20	12.2
HKR120	10.3	10.1	98	51.7 (7.14)	51.5 (7.22)	100	37.2	19.0	50	18.2
PR106	8.9	8.6	97	44.5 (6.74)	42.8 (6.62)	96	42.4	24.6	58	13.5
IET8113	9.7	8.6	89	48.4 (6.96)	36.1 (6.00)	78	40.6	19.1	78	14.7
IET8116	12.3	11.0	98	51.2 (7.21)	36.2 (6.01)	85	39.6	15.6	62	15.7
Pakistan Basmati	14.4	14.4	100	67.2 (8.26)	66.0 (8.19)	100	71.9	60.6	84	52.0
LSD (0.05)	2.8	4.0		(0.60)	(1.75)		9.3	4.7		4.7

^aAv of 20 hills. ^bAv of 20 leaves. Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{n+1}$ values.

of Sep, when the rice crop was at the booting to panicle emergence stage. No variety was untouched, but varieties

with relatively broader leaves had less infestation. The pest caused 30-80% yield loss.